

Open Book Futures InfoHub scoping report

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Document overview

Project name	Open Book Futures
Project acronym	OBF

Start date	May 2023
End date	April 2026
Contributing WP(s)	WP2, WP3
WP lead(s)	Joe Deville, Tom Grady
Deliverable identifier	The establishment of a knowledge base to provide comprehensive resources on alternative funding models and modes of publishing, acquiring and archiving open access books (WPs 2, 3, 6)

Version history

Version	Created/modified	Comments
0.0	10 July 2024	For internal review
0.1	31 July 2024	For external review
0.2	03 September 2024	For Zenodo
0.3	01 December 2024	Internal, after suggestions
0.4	11 February 2024	Internal, after suggestions
0.5	11 February 2025	For Zenodo

Acronyms

Acronyms are written out in full in the first instance, followed by their acronym in parentheses, and from there on in referred to by their acronym.

ACRL	Association of College & Research Libraries
AEUP	Association of European University Presses
ALPSP	Association of Learned and Professional

	Society Publishers
AUP	Association of University Presses
BPCs	Book Processing Charges
C4DISC	Coalition for Diversity and Inclusion in Scholarly Communications
CAP	Central Access Point
COPIM	Community-led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs
DCC	Diamond Capacity Center
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DOAB	Directory of Open Access Books
DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard
EDIB	Equality Diversity Inclusion and Belonging
ERA	European Research Area
EU-LAC	Association of University Publishers of Latin America and the Caribbean
IFLA	International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions
IOAP	Irish Open Access Publishers
IOI	Invest in Open Infrastructure
IP	Institutional Publisher
KU	Knowledge Unlatched
LPC	Library Publishing Coalition

NUP	New University Press
OA	Open Access
OABN	Open Access Books Network
OAD	Open Access Directory
OAPEN	Open Access Publishing in European Networks
OASPA	Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association
OBC	Open Book Collective
OBF	Open Book Futures
OIPA	Open Institutional Publishing Association
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
OTF	Opening the Future
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
ORC	Open Research Community
ORL	Open Research Library
OS	Open Science
PALOMERA	Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area
PLACE	Publishers Learning and Community Exchange
PRISM	Peer Review Information Service for Monographs

RED	Research England Development
REF	Research Excellence Framework
RoW	Rest of World
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SciELO	Scientific Electronic Library Online
SCURL	Scottish Confederation of University and Research Libraries
SIG	Special Interest Group
SPARC EU	Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition EU
TAs	Transitional Agreements (AKA Transformative Agreements)
TOME	Towards an Open Monograph Ecosystem
UKRI	United Kingdom Research and Innovation
Ulibros	Libros académicos y universitarios de Iberoamérica (Academic and University books from Latin America)
WG	Working Group
WIPO	World Intellectual Property Organisation

Executive summary

Work Packages 2 and 3 of the Open Book Futures (OBF) project focus on exploring and supporting sustainable open access (OA) books publishing. A key deliverable of the OBF project is the **establishment of a knowledge base to provide comprehensive resources on alternative funding models and modes of publishing, acquiring and archiving open access books (WPs 2, 3, 6), alongside new training and guidance on archiving and preservation best practice (WP7) (hereafter referred to as the InfoHub).** The InfoHub will (a) develop resources for stakeholders, (b) consolidate existing resources, (c) promote business

models best practice, and (d) showcase project work on metadata, experimental publishing and archiving. By providing a comprehensive tool suite of resources we will **accelerate outreach to libraries, publishers, academics and the wider public, to advocate for, advise on and encourage open access publishing and initiatives.**

Drawing on a variety of sources produced within and outside the OBF project, this scoping report presents an overview of existing resources and guidance for OA book publishing, a gap analysis, and our initial recommendations for the OBF working group (WG) to consider, all of which will be used to scope the direction and final format of the InfoHub.

During our research, we discovered that a great many resources, guidelines, and toolkits have been developed in the last few years, many of which are regularly maintained and updated, and that many others are currently under development. A few gaps were identified, most of which were outside of our expertise.

As a result, our preliminary conclusion is two-fold. Firstly, we believe that, given the wealth of high-quality resources already available, some of which are already outputs of this project, one valuable activity is in collating these, and categorising them, providing a central sign-posting location for external resources. **Our aim is to complement rather than re-develop.** Secondly, one of the lacunae which was well within the competencies of the participating project members was a resource on transitioning publishers from closed to open access, and we therefore propose that that will be one of other main purposes of this InfoHub.

OA is now a fixture in the book publishing space; we need to make sure that as it grows further (which it will!), it is well-resourced and that reliable resources for all stakeholders groups are available and well sign-posted. OBF concluded that some further elaboration on some topics (by us) was necessary within our own remit.

Introduction

OBF launched in May 2023, and is set to run until April 2026. It is a new initiative supported by Arcadia¹ and the Research England Development (RED) Fund² that will build on the pioneering work of the COPIM project (2019–2023).³ OBF is led by Lancaster University and will significantly expand key infrastructures created by COPIM to achieve a step change in the ambition, scope and impact of community-led OA book publishing.

It is important to set out the current context in which we are planning to create, and curate, our own resource. The wider OA (monograph) landscape has grown, matured and consolidated in

¹ <https://www.arcadiahfund.org.uk/>

² <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/browse-our-areas-of-investment-and-support/research-england-development-fund/>

³ <https://copim.pubpub.org/copim-project>

many senses in the last few years. Firstly, via funder mandates, such as that of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), which expanded its requirements from journals to books in January 2024, and REF 2029 who is currently consulting with the sector around their plans to expand their OA requirements to include books from January 2026.⁴ The number of OA books being published has expanded in the last few years,⁵ the growth of OA at large commercial publishers,⁶ and the expansion of scholar-led and commercial presses from Gold to Diamond OA publishing schemes such as Bloomsbury, Taylor and Francis and De Gruyter, which have complicated and extended this in a number of ways.

Alongside these developments, there has been the great growth in OA infrastructural development, which remains ongoing,⁷ and in collective OA endeavours, for example, the creation of shared principles, guidelines and infrastructure in the European Research Area (ERA) at more formalised, international levels (the EC-funded DIAMAS and PALOMERA projects, both currently active). New OA networks at national levels have also emerged such as OIPA in the UK and IOAP in Ireland, and infrastructural projects such as OBF itself. Other publisher and library networks have also begun to produce their own resources, aimed at their users and audiences, around OA, while smaller, more ad-hoc projects have also arisen to provide their own resources (as covered later in this report).

As a result this is, in many ways, currently a very crowded field for resources. It is also a very scattered one, and one that covers an increasingly large range of subjects from technical (e.g. metadata and archiving), through to financial and editorial ones, among others. As OA is becoming an entrenched feature of book publishing, it is important that authors, libraries, and publishers are all provided with, and pointed towards, good resources to support them. Therefore, we started by undertaking a scoping report and gap analysis to evaluate the current landscape of information resources on this topic more precisely.

This report presents an overview of the existing landscape of OA resources on a national, European and global level. It will share and analyse existing OA toolkits / tool suites (and other sources of information) as well as examine those in development as part of other projects. The report aims to provide comprehensive insights into the existing level of support and ascertain gaps in the market that could be filled by the OBF InfoHub [or not!]. The outcome of the report will

⁴ Since the first draft of this report, the decision was made that there will be no longform open access mandate for REF 2029. See: <https://www.ref.ac.uk/news/early-decisions-made-on-ref-2029-open-access-policy/> However, REF have confirmed that there will be a longform mandate in subsequent REF assessments.

⁵ It is difficult to measure this directly but there are clear indirect indications; for example, a search of history books on DOAB shows an increase from 95 books published in 2015, to 193 books published in 2020, and again to 251 books published in 2023. A search of medicine and nursing books shows an increase from 95 books published in 2015, to 146 books published in 2020, and again to 305 books published in 2023.

⁶ This is also difficult to measure directly. Many commercial publishers have had open access options since the early to mid 2010s, but the actual numbers of publications have often increased over this time. Using the DOAB data with a few publishers: Springer Nature 2013: 41 books, 2018: 201 books, 2023: 538 books. T&F 2013: 40 books, 2018: 217 books, 2023: 720 books. De Gruyter 2013: 84 books, 2018: 168 books, 2023: 208 books.

⁷ <https://investinopen.org/state-of-open-infrastructure-2024/sooi-adoption-2024/>

steer the development of the OBF InfoHub, including format, platform and content, and shape thinking on discovery and outreach.

Methodology

We began by defining some very broad parameters for resources that we were interested in; that they were made specifically in support of OA, that they related to long-form publication, and that they provided guidance and information that was broadly applicable, rather than, e.g. being the guidelines for an individual publisher.

We first began by listing resources of which we were already aware, and then began further horizon scanning and searching purposefully for additional resources. We gathered information from various platforms and sources across the UK and more widely to examine the availability, extent and reach of existing tool suites and other information hubs as well as determining target audiences to establish potential crossover and opportunities for signposting and collaboration. We were aware of other projects that were in the development stage ([see Appendix 4](#)) and whose outcome would also be a knowledge sharing toolkit. As final content of these resources is still to be determined, analysis is limited but we have included these to support our rationale and give this report a richer flavour.

Once we had as complete a list as possible, we created a Google Sheet⁸ so we could compare the resources along different parameters, such as audience, resource type. We also undertook a SWOT analysis and assessed sustainability (Appendix 1). The summaries of each resource we analysed are listed in greater detail in [Appendix 2](#).

The remit of this report was, technically, very large and wide-ranging, reflecting the growth of OA and the OA books landscape in every sense. The first step in conducting a gap analysis is to define the scope and objectives of the analysis; given the amount of resources that could be classed as relevant to the scoping exercise, we had to set limitations. Firstly defining the broad parameters mentioned above, and secondly, applying a time frame for the gathering and assessing of resources. We recognise that there may be gaps in the areas of knowledge or practice that our study does not address or fully cover, and that could be explored further by other researchers.

We would also like to emphasise that OBF is primarily a UK-based project, and the authors are working with a highly UK and Anglophone-focussed perspective. While we have endeavoured to make sure that we include relevant resources from around the world, we are aware that we are likely to have missed many, particularly those that are not in English.⁹

⁸ This is an internal document and was removed from the public version of this report.

⁹ After this initial phase, we took steps to mitigate this by seeking guidance from colleagues and frequent collaborators elsewhere, e.g. someone at Project Muse is happy to look at this and fill in gaps from a US perspective.

We hope that this will be mitigated somewhat by some of the resources we are planning to point to, such as the PALOMERA Knowledge Base, which covers policies from across the ERA, or the IFLA Open Access Vocabularies glossary, which contains some translations. We can also ensure that we point visitors to resources such as the OPERAS National Nodes, which may be able to provide them with more localised guidance as necessary. Nevertheless, we are also aware that these are all European, and that we are likely to be missing many resources from RoW.

We also asked the Open Access Books Network (OABN) for access to some of the feedback they received from a survey undertaken last year regarding what resources would be useful to their network members. Some of the main pieces of feedback was the need for greater clarity and information about Equity, Diversity, Inclusion & Belonging (EDIB), a desire for success stories/best practice around OA book publishing, and for more information about non-European regions, which we kept in mind while researching this report.

Overview of resources

This section includes a list of the majority of the resources we reviewed in the comparison spreadsheet (Appendix 1) as part of our desk based research. Some appear in both lists as there is considerable crossover. After some initial analysis, we felt it inappropriate to point to some of these resources ([Appendices 2-4](#)), for example, individual publisher web pages (unless of course they included more general OA for books information and / or author case studies), or information relating to individual countries OA policies as these were covered by PALOMERA or it would be unfair to signpost to one and not another. Additionally, although some of the resources included do not represent the views of the authors or the OBF from an ethical standpoint, it is necessary to get a holistic viewpoint and so they have been included. The resources have been divided up via the following categories: **existing resources, useful organisations, projects and platforms, and those in development**. Please note, they are not listed in any particular order or ranking, merely the sequence in which we discovered them and added them to the internal comparison spreadsheet.

Existing resources

This section includes resources such as toolkits, websites sign-posting to resources, directories and author case studies.

1. [OABN](#)
 - a. [Resources for Publishers](#)
 - b. [Resources for Libraries](#)
 - c. [Resources for Authors](#)
 - d. [Resources for Funders](#)
 - e. ['Mythbusters' videos](#)

- f. [Blog series 'Around the World with the OABN'](#)
2. [Jisc New University Press toolkit](#)
3. [C4DISC Toolkit](#) for Journal Editors and Publishers: Building Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, and Accessibility in Editorial Roles and Peer Review
4. [Toolkit](#) to foster Open Access Agreements for Smaller Independent Publishers
5. [OAPEN OA Books Toolkit](#) (general)
 - a. [OAPEN OA Books Toolkit](#) (life cycle)
 - b. [OAPEN OA Books Toolkit](#) (FAQ)
 - c. [OAPEN OA Books Toolkit](#) (Keywords and Glossary sections)
 - d. [OAPEN OA Books Toolkit](#) (Author success stories)
6. [ACRL Scholarly Communication Toolkit](#): Open Access Policies & Publishing toolkit
7. [Open Access Directory](#) (OAD)
8. [OBC Toolkit](#) for Small and Scholar-Led Open Access Publishers
9. [COPIM's toolkit](#) for running an Opening the Future programme at an academic press
10. [Open Book Environment \(OBE\) Dashboard](#)
11. [Cookbook for Open Access books](#)
12. [IFLA Open Access Vocabularies](#)
13. [PALOMERA Knowledge Base](#)
14. [How to Begin the OA Transition: a guide for smaller and specialist publishers](#)
15. [Supporting learned society, subject association, and smaller specialist publishers to transition to open access book publishing](#)
16. [Springer OA author testimonials](#)
17. [Bloomsbury author case studies](#)
18. [University of Oxford Open book case studies](#)
19. [Lancaster University: Author Testimonies and Case Studies](#)
20. [Classifying Open Access business models](#)
21. [SCURL EDI toolkit](#)
22. [Business Models for Open Access Books](#)
23. [Open Access Network: Open Access Books summary Infohub](#)
24. [Sherpa Open Access for Books \(Jisc\)](#)
25. [OPERAS Pathfinder](#)
26. [University of Sheffield: OA author case studies](#)
27. [Open access book publishing: a series editor writes](#)
28. [Scottish Universities Press: Breaking down borders between academia and the rest of the world: A conversation with Tim Ingold and his co-authors](#)
29. [UKRI: Researchers' experiences of publishing academic books open access. Case studies on open access publishing](#)
30. [ASK UP](#)
31. [Experimental Publishing Compendium](#)
32. [Contracts in Publishing: A toolkit for authors and publishers \(WIPO Publications\)](#)
33. [How to Start an Open Access Journal: 2024 Small Publisher Primer](#)

34. [Towards an Open Monograph Ecosystem \(TOME\)](#)
 - a. [TOME: Author Testimonials](#)
 - b. [TOME Report: The Cost to Publish TOME Monographs](#)
 - c. [TOME Stakeholder Value Assessment: Final Report](#)
35. [University of Essex: OA fund author testimonials](#)
36. [EIFL Report 'Landscape of no-fee open access publishing in Africa'](#)
37. [Cookbook for Open Access books](#)
38. [Open Science resources | Latin America](#)
39. [OA Book Stakeholders \(African Context\)](#)
40. [Canadian Library Journal Publishing: A Primer](#)
41. [Open Access Australasia](#)
42. [How to flip your journal: A guide to more equitable publishing with Diamond Open Access](#)
43. [Guidance on managing copyright under UKRI open access policy](#)
44. [Publishing under the UKRI open access policy: copyright and Creative Commons licences](#)
45. [An introduction to UKRI's fund for longform outputs](#)
46. [Plan S: New tool to assess equity in scholarly communication models](#)
47. [Manchester University Press Alt Text Guidelines](#)
48. [DIAMAS Best Practices checklist for Diamond OA publishers](#)
49. [DIAMAS Resources & Guidelines](#)
50. [European University Association: The new university Open Access checklist](#)
51. [Library Partnership Rating](#)

Useful organisations, projects and platforms

This section includes organisations, projects and platforms relevant to OA book publishing.

52. [OABN](#)
53. [Thoth](#)
54. OPERAS Metrics
55. [Open Access Institutional Publishers](#)
 - a. [Useful resources](#)
56. [OASPA](#)
57. [AUP](#)
58. [Library Publishing Coalition \(LPC\)](#)
59. [Association of European University Presses \(AEUP\)](#)
60. [OAPEN](#)
 - a. [OAPEN: Online library of open access books](#)
 - b. [OABN](#)

- c. [DOAB](#)
- d. [PRISM: Peer Review Information Service for Monographs](#)
- 61. [Open access tracking project](#)
- 62. [Project Muse](#)
- 63. [Open Research Library](#)
- 64. [Open Research Community](#)
- 65. [JSTOR Open Access](#)
- 66. [The Publishers Learning and Community Exchange \(PLACE\)](#)
- 67. [SciELO](#)
- 68. [Ulibros](#)
- 69. [SPARC EU](#)

In development

This section includes projects that are in progress, and whose outcomes will be an InfoHub / toolkit potentially similar to ours. Many of them will deliver theirs ahead of ours which will be a useful steer and to avoid duplication and encourage mutual sign-posting.

- 70. [Information Power project](#)
- 71. [DIAMAS project](#)
 - a. [Diamond OA Standard \(DOAS\)](#)
 - b. [Common Access Point \(CAP\)](#)
- 72. [Invest in Open Infrastructure \(IOI\) Infra Finder tool](#)
- 73. [OASPA recommendations to increase equity in open access](#)
- 74. OIPA 'resources hub' [no link yet]
- 75. Copim OBF project WP5 deliverable is to publish "Guidance on accessibility standards implementation (online toolkit) [no link yet]

Results

Our desk based research showed that there is a wealth of OA book resources out there already; there are numerous high-quality, recent, and sustainable resources that have already been published, or which are nearing publication. We could have continued horizon scanning indefinitely but had to set time limitations in the interest of delivering this report on time, and to allow time scoping, planning and delivering our InfoHub.

Whereas the majority of the resources we found are reliable, trustworthy and sustainable; others we did not feel confident enough to analyse fully. Please see the comparison spreadsheet

Appendix 1.¹⁰ The results have informed our preliminary conclusions, as outlined in the following section of the report.

Preliminary conclusions

The debate around open access books in the UK continues to be lively, and with EC-projects such as PALOMERA focusing on book policies, we are seeing a similar trend of increasing interest in OA books on a larger scale.

As mentioned in the previous section, our research has concluded that there are already numerous high quality, recent, and sustainable resources that have already been published, or which are nearing publication. It is clear that there is already a lot of duplication out there e.g. signposting to the same resources such as the OA books toolkit and platforms such as the OAPEN online library. This will only continue exponentially as OA for books becomes more entrenched due to factors such as inclusion in funder policies, ever growing financial pressures on library budgets and increased advocacy from the sector for more equitable publishing models.

Most notably, there are several large and comprehensive toolkits which cover the processes of setting up scholar-led or institutional born-OA presses, and the OAPEN toolkit which comprehensively covers the author experience for OA monographs, and which is also widely used by other stakeholders as a major source of information and guidance.

We also noted other large, international resources such as the PALOMERA Knowledge Base which acts as a central repository for mandates and other guidance documents from across the ERA, and the IOI Infra Finder tool which provides guidance on open infrastructure options. In addition to these large and comprehensive resources, there are many smaller initiatives and projects that fill a plethora of smaller niches. This suggests that our InfoHub could save research performing institutions (RPOs) time and resources by acting as a reliable and responsible gatekeeper to a list of trusted resources.

The limitations of our project were also clear. Sourcing non-European and non-UK resources has been challenging and after this initial scoping report, we will focus some of our efforts on seeking additional resources. Language barriers will make this difficult in some parts of the world, and we would value any input on this aspect from the WG.

As noted in the introduction, OABN members had called for resources on EDIB. We identified two toolkits on this subject, one by SSP and one by SCURL. However, while the SCURL toolkit was

¹⁰ This is an internal document and was removed from the public version of this report.

thorough and considered and had guidelines (e.g. relating to hiring practices) that were widely applicable, it was, due to the nature of SCURL, a very library-focussed resource. The SSP toolkit, while it was aimed at publishers, was not focussed on OA, and mentioned it only in passing, suggesting that publishers use 'transitional' agreements (TAs), and was otherwise suited to large publishers with extensive human and financial resources and reporting tools, which does not represent the majority of publishers. Therefore, we feel that EDIB resources, particularly for smaller publishers, are still lacking. Copim WP5 is in the process of developing guidance, as an online toolkit, on accessibility standards implementation, which we will certainly point to from this resource, particularly because there is currently no comparable resource on accessibility for OA books. But while accessibility (covered by WP5) is a core component of EDIB, they are not synonymous. However, we feel that creating a new resource for EDIB is outside our remit and, in any case, requires knowledge and expertise that are not our own. This is possibly something that could be looked at by the new Library Relationship & Accessibility manager (based at Lancaster University, funded by OBF), as part of their remit when in post.

Additionally, regarding EDIB resources, it was noted that DIAMAS is developing EDIB resources for Diamond OA publishers to be part of DOAS and the self-assessment tool. While this will be primarily aimed at journal publishers, many of the resources will be relevant to books, and the resource will be expanded in the future to accommodate books more formally.

However, we identified a few main areas where our InfoHub could contribute meaningfully to this crowded field.

The first was to create a **signposting exercise** which draws on many of the existing strengths of the COPIM project itself. The Copim community has put a lot of work in the last few years into building a trusted community that is both recognised and respected by the wider open access community. It therefore made sense for us to use this to create a trusted resource, a one stop shop, so to speak, for resources that will signpost to relevant and trusted external groups, toolkits, reports etc. As Copim has produced its own toolkits and resources, and is partially composed of organisations such as OBC and Thoth, it is therefore not an entirely dispassionate or detached body to judge resources and organisation. However, one of the major stated aims of the second phase of Copim is to 'build and nourish' 'a more diverse, scholar-led, community-owned, and not-for-profit publishing ecosystem',¹¹ i.e., our work goes beyond what we ourselves have created. Additionally, it feels in keeping with Copim's objectives to serve a wide community that is, individually, scaling small, for us to act as a contact point for a very wide variety of resources, from and for different stakeholders whose common interest is OA long-form publications: their creation, funding, and dissemination, and the environment in which they are produced.

¹¹ <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/introducing-open-book-futures-a-copim-community-project/release/1>

One additional area that struck us as useful, and which is represented in the category above of **'Useful organisations, projects and platforms'** is that, as the OA field grows, so do the number of relevant bodies, and that a list with a brief description (including any relational links between them such as between OAPEN and DOAB) would, in and of itself, be a useful resource.

One of the gaps flagged in the OABN survey was also found to be quite well-resourced in our research, which was that of **open access author success stories**, particularly positive author experiences, as evidence for the viability of OA publishing. These are generally produced by individual publishers and hosted on their own pages, so creating a centralised collection of these is an area where our signposting exercise could be widely valuable. However, we would like to source more of these from around the world, as our current findings were virtually all UK-based. Building on this, initial feedback from our WG identified that **library OA success stories**, such as those at Sheffield, Lancaster, York and elsewhere would also be valuable as an evidence collection for other libraries who are trying to direct their funding to OA. This would involve collating existing resources, reports, and webinar write-ups, and commissioning further information from libraries. We would also need to make sure that we include libraries from beyond the UK. The WG noted that WP7 may be able to provide useful contacts for this as part of their National Libraries Network. Regarding library OA success stories, it was suggested that a public call for these could be disseminated, including via the OABN and via OBC/OtF library member lists in summer / autumn 2024.

Additionally, we have identified a further gap in the existing toolkits which we are well set up to fill. The current resources comprehensively and clearly cover setting up a new OA publisher, be that a New University Press (NUP) via the Jisc Toolkit, or more generally a new OA press as per the OBC Toolkit. However, currently there are very few resources that touch on the logistics of **flipping existing traditional publishers to Diamond OA**, as opposed to charging book processing charges (BPCs) which many of them do. This is a resource that is both necessary and highly relevant to WP3 for several reasons.

The first reason is that as part of Copim phase 1, a toolkit for implementing Opening the Future (OtF) was published in 2021. However, it is now somewhat out of date due to the developments since then. Additionally, it was not taken up by other publishers subsequently, although it informed at least one other project.¹² But due to the increasing uptake of OA for books, for funder mandate reasons alongside others, which cannot be sustained via Gold OA funding, publishers will need to engage with mechanisms such as OtF more and more. Therefore, we believe that it is worth turning this original toolkit into a more substantial one, and including it as part of the wider resources on the InfoHub.

¹² <https://uplopen.com/for-libraries> 'UPLOpen leverages insights gained from previous open access eBook initiatives including TOME, Luminos, and Opening the Future.'

First Working Group meeting: outcomes and suggestions

We therefore identified what we see as the best purpose of the InfoHub, and which gaps are within our own competency to fill. We took this report, and the appendix of resources, to our internal WG for their input; this version of the report reflects this additional expertise.

Initial conclusions

- This resource should primarily be aimed at publishers. This is for several reasons; firstly, that authors already have a large and comprehensive toolkit from OAPEN, and there are many resources pertaining directly to libraries. Secondly, that many of the lacunae we identified in the OA guidance landscape were specifically for publishers. And thirdly, because many publishers already work with, or would recognise, the Copim brand and community ethos
- This report should be disseminated more widely. It was suggested that we should disseminate a version of this report to the OPERAS nodes and other relevant Special Interest Groups (SIGs) in order to help localise and expand our list and to ensure that we do not miss important resources unnecessarily. An external partner at a US organisation had also already agreed to see if there were important US resources missing from this. We hope that through these, and by following up on the suggestion to ask WP7 (Archiving & Digital Preservation) to disseminate this through their networks, that we will be able to find more resources that are not UK-specific, and some that are not Anglophone (although assessing these may raise some difficulties, and we may need to point to them with an acknowledgement that we ourselves are not able to read them, but that they have been sourced via trusted external partners)
- During the meeting, some further resources were suggested that have now been included; we appreciate these amendments
- While this is primarily a resource for OA books, it was agreed that, where relevant, it would be appropriate to link to journal-specific resources, for projects that will expand into books such as DIAMAS, or where there are overarching themes that touch on both books and journals, such as ethics guidance
- We also raised in this meeting how to navigate the fact that while Copim is focussed on Diamond OA specifically, many OA resources are not. It was decided that we would emphasise prominently on the InfoHub that we, as a project, have a Diamond focus, and that we would put an emphasis on open publishing with no author costs, while still linking to broader OA resources that are relevant. However, we would exclude ones that were clearly counter to the aims of Copim such as, theoretically, a resource on how to

implement BPCs as a publisher. It was also noted that this principle, and that of including overarching journal resources, would also help us to keep Copim’s remit in mind as we decide what is in and out of scope for inclusion on the InfoHub

- We covered the topic of how will the quality, diversity and applicability of the content on the InfoHub be assured? It was agreed that our internal review of all the resources, combined with further input from the WG, was sufficient, but that further guidance on its long-term home and hosting might reasonably be sought

Outstanding actions

Several queries and tasks remain outstanding before we finalise the shape and direction of our InfoHub:

We need to decide where it will be hosted, including establishing what the available options are (this includes considering the long-term home and maintenance / upkeep of this resource, as the Copim project ends in Spring 2026). We have a few options, to be considered along the different parameters of sustainability and usability.

Name	Pros	Cons
Copim PubPub ¹³	Already pointed to as a resource; already read and used; easy to use; amenable to this sort of work	Perhaps would tip us even further to reliance on PubPub as a platform; means that the site content would reside on commercial servers outside our control. Additionally, with recent changes there that are still being understood, the viability of this is no longer clear.
BookStack ¹⁴ installation (or other installation) embedded on copim.ac.uk	An .ac.uk address will appear trustworthy to people beyond those aware of/engaged with Copim; the website will be hosted for quite a while; BookStack was used for the	Requires technical competence to install; needs to be maintained; Coventry University Digital Services currently only have a contract for this server until 2026.

¹³ See: <https://copim.pubpub.org/>

¹⁴ See: <https://www.bookstackapp.com/>

	OBC toolkit ¹⁵ and is very user-friendly and attractive; if installed on the Copim server (hosted by Coventry University) we will have full control over the site and its content which allows for long-term archiving and preservation	Additionally, much of this work would in reality fall to SB so it requires discussion with him (in Summer/Autumn 2024)
Zenodo. ¹⁶	Good long-term sustainability, straightforward to use and update	Means that the InfoHub could only be a static document which is not ideal - while versioning is possible, it is unlikely that external parties would approach this as an ongoing Infohub and may be less likely to engage with it; means that the site content would reside on commercial servers outside our control
OAPEN	OAPEN is a trusted external resource and this may help the Infohub reach more people, its long-term sustainability would be good	We might need to adapt it to their requirements, we don't know what their acceptance processes, structures or timescales are and they may be too lengthy for our deliverable date, it may be confusing that they already have their own toolkit
DIAMAS European Capacity Hub. ¹⁷	Greater exposure to non-UK audience, potentially more secure long-term hosting than some other options	Not due to go live early 2025

¹⁵ See <https://toolkit.openbookcollective.org/>

¹⁶ See: <https://zenodo.org/>

¹⁷ An action on this is to ensure that the executive summary of this report is clear and comprehensive so that it can be sent to DIAMAS for consideration

OPERAS was also floated as an idea, as this is a resource for Diamond OA books, of which there are not many. A WG member suggested that we could look to utilise the EU server set-up OPERAS is developing to host site and content, which would provide a community to maintain beyond the project.

We need to write a work/mission statement, based on WG meetings and earlier project discussions. This will be a collaborative endeavour by the WG, and will be shared with all OBF colleagues for agreement by the end of August (M4 of Year 2), and then added to the timeline of work.

As elaborated on above in our methodology limitations section, we are aware that our selection of resources has been shaped by the author's lack of knowledge of the OA books landscape outside of the Anglophone world and our language limitations. We would like to point to any relevant resources in other areas and languages than our own and would be grateful for suggestions. **We would be pleased to consider non UK/EU/US resources or author / library success stories recommended by readers. If you would like to submit some, please get in touch at info@copim.ac.uk.**

Categorisation of resources

For the signposting exercise component, we need to categorise and group the resources we will link under different headings. This is partly to clarify our perspectives on what groups of stakeholders this InfoHub is for, to get a sense of how these relate to one another, and to identify what areas have fewer existing resources that we could continue horizon scanning for. (N.b. resources can belong to more than one category).

Some initial suggestions for categories are:

- Full toolkits
- EDIB resources
- Author experiences of publishing OA
- Financial models (with a focus on moving towards OA from closed access publishing)
- Open infrastructure projects
- Definitions (glossaries)
- Important organisations and projects relating to OA monographs and Diamond OA
- Diamond-specific resources
- OA networks

It was suggested that these categories should also be grouped by the categories in the Copim OBF bid:

- Experimental publishing
- Funding models
- Accessibility
- Metadata management
- Preservation/archiving
- Governance best practices

The WG agreed that these are useful categories about different aspects, along with others such as 'Author experiences of publishing OA', 'Glossary', 'Directory of organisations', 'Full toolkits'. As such, we will formulate our category list more along these lines.

Summary

Appendices

[Appendix 1 is redacted from this version]

Appendix 2. Summary of existing resources

OABN

Resources for Publishers

New university press toolkit

Online guide supporting and giving guidance to new university presses and library-led publishing ventures. It is a trusted and valued resource, although it is at the start of a process to archive it to a new platform (no timeline yet available).

See: <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/guides/new-university-press-toolkit>

A Focused Toolkit for Journal Editors and Publishers: Building Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, and Accessibility in Editorial Roles and Peer Review (C4DISC)

The toolkit is focused on building representation among peer reviewers and fostering equity in the actions of peer reviewers. It is also dedicated to building DEIA into core aspects of the wider editorial endeavor. While it has detailed, and in places, useful, guidance, and is very new (published May 2024) the majority of the advice is only relevant to very large and well-funded outfits with robust reporting tools, mostly with a focus on journals. It also mentions open access as a facet of equity, but suggests using transformative agreements.

See: <https://c4disc.pubpub.org/toolkit-editors-and-publishers>

Toolkit to foster Open Access Agreements for Smaller Independent Publishers (cOAlitionS)

This toolkit was developed by Information Power, commissioned by cOAlition S and ALPSP. It provides concise guidance, example licences and data templates for smaller publishers to use while negotiating agreements with libraries. It is journal-focussed, and there is a forthcoming Information Power report (Winter 2024) which focuses on books.

See: <https://zenodo.org/records/6502325>

OAPEN: OA books toolkit (includes general info, publication life cycle, FAQs and author success stories)

This toolkit aims to help book authors to better understand open access book publishing and to increase trust in open access books. Authors can find relevant articles on open access book publishing following the research lifecycle, by browsing frequently asked questions or by searching with keywords.

In our research we broke this wide-ranging and comprehensive author-focussed tool into three sections; the Life Cycle, the FAQs, and the Keywords and Glossary. The first is a series of articles laid out in the 'life cycle' of a book from choosing a publisher through to publication, dissemination and reuse, the second a list of FAQs about OA books that link to brief answers, and also to associated Life Cycle articles. The third are the glossary, a list of frequently used terms to do with OA books, and the keywords, which is a similar (but not identical) list which links to articles in the toolkit which contain that word.

The toolkit is extremely thorough, detailed, clear, comprehensive, well-referenced and useful, and should be used as the main place to point OA authors to. It is also being regularly updated and maintained, and is likely to be supported for a long time as it is at OAPEN.

See: <https://www.oabooks-toolkit.org/>

Scholarly Communication Toolkit: Open Access Policies & Publishing toolkit

This resource has also pointed to some other toolkits that could be interesting as a lot of them cover negotiating agreements from library POV. However, the authors do not personally feel qualified to assess this particular resource given it is a North American resource (other than noting it has not been updated for a few years).

See: <https://acrl.libguides.com/scholcomm/toolkit/openaccess>

Open Access Directory

The Open Access Directory (OAD) is a wiki / compendium of simple factual lists about open access (OA) to science and scholarship, maintained by the OA community at large. While very journal-focussed it does have some book and wider OA lists/information. It contains lists and data that is not replicated in other resources but would be interesting to some, e.g. around the history of open access. It is more relevant for those interested in open access in and of itself than many other listed resources. However, its information is out of date in some highly relevant places such as OA book business models, which was a page last updated in 2020 and which is missing recent developments.

See: https://oad.simmons.edu/oadwiki/Main_Page

Open Book Collective toolkit

The Open Book Collective toolkit is for small, scholar-led OA publishers who are either setting up a press or seeking to improve its operations. It covers a broad range of aspects about setting up a press and building one up logistically and reputationally. It also provides case studies. It and the Jisc NUP toolkit are complimentary.

See: <https://toolkit.openbookcollective.org/>

COPIM's toolkit for running an Opening the Future programme at an academic press

This document sets out how Copim implemented the OtF model, including the documentation of challenges, resources, timetables, and activities. It is intended as a roadmap for other presses that wish to implement an 'Opening the Future'-esque model. It is the only toolkit dedicated to flipping book publishing from closed to open (although the Information Power report due in December will likely render this incorrect). It is now slightly out of date as many of these funding models have developed greatly since 2020. It is also not currently very user-friendly and has not been widely adopted. One aim of this InfoHub is to expand on and update this, and make it a more navigable and usable resource.

See: <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/copim-toolkit-for-running-an-opening-the-future-programme/release/3> or <https://zenodo.org/records/7003979>

Open Book Environment (OBE) Dashboard

The Open Book Environment is a transparency dashboard about publishers, aimed at authors (and their funders) focussing on author fees, licencing, their policies on self-archiving, waiver and discount information, and any stated price justification. It is a very recent resource (2023) however, its longevity is unclear because it is a Google sheet maintained by two volunteer contributors. It also currently does not cover many publishers, but is being added to over time. It may be worth contacting the creators to ask about their long-term plans for the resource.

See: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/15TtYZtYNamjo-SZ6_7hI3pY64LeAwC2EIBSDFLxNmN4/edit#gid=59142032

Cookbook for Open Access books

This book describes the experiences of setting up a community-based publisher, Language Science Press. It discusses the main principles of community-based publishing and gives a very granular breakdown of the different tasks. The discussion of the different tasks is complemented by readings, time lines, and a list of time sinks. This book is complemented by the business model (<https://zenodo.org/record/1286972>), open business data, and a spreadsheet for drafting and calculating own business models.

See: <https://zenodo.org/records/1286925>

IFLA Open Access Vocabularies

This resource is a PDF of some key terminology used in open access. Unlike many glossaries, it does cite its sources for definition - but this is also a weakness because it does not, therefore, appear like they have taken a range of definitions and collated/merged them into one broad definition. Additionally, this appears to be aimed at journals. One benefit is that it does contain some translations, while other glossaries that may be more comprehensive and considered (such as the OAPEN toolkit one) are in English only. This was produced in May 2024 so it is very up to date.

See: <https://repository.ifla.org/handle/123456789/3272>

PALOMERA Knowledge Base

The Knowledge Base is a collection of documents, such as reports, policies, survey results and statistics, relevant to Open Access (OA) policies regarding OA books in the European Research Area. The collection was created as part of the PALOMERA project. It is an unparalleled resource in terms of providing a centralised hub for OA documents from across the ERA in a

range of languages, varying greatly in scope from individual publisher guidelines to national mandates. We definitely need to link to it although it is not very user-friendly or searchable.

See: <https://knowledgebase.oabooks-toolkit.org/communities/>

How to Begin the OA Transition: a guide for smaller and specialist publishers

This guide, the result of a collaboration between UKRI, ALPSP, the British Academy, OASPA and Information Power, was published in 2025. It provides advice and tools for learned societies and other smaller specialist publishers seeking strategies and business models for transitioning to OA. It provides guidance on advocating for OA to necessary stakeholders such as board members, potential pain or clarification points for any commercial publishing partners the smaller publisher may have, and a detailed guide to different available revenue models. It also provides practical guidance on licences, metadata, archiving, and tracking title performance.

See: <https://zenodo.org/records/14679095>

Supporting learned society, subject association, and smaller specialist publishers to transition to open access book publishing

This report, the result of a collaboration between UKRI, ALPSP, the British Academy, OASPA and Information Power, was published in 2025. It was produced in the context of the UKRI policy change in 2024 that longform publications of UKRI-funded research were to be published open access. It seeks to understand the challenges faced by smaller, specialist publishers of business models, scale, and other issues as they seek to implement open access. Among its many conclusions and recommendations, it notes the tension between OA models being largely reliant on library support, while libraries find it difficult to turn their budgets to supporting OA books. They also note that without improvement in the supply chain (especially at the discoverability stage) it will be hard for smaller publishers to work without support from larger publishing partners. New open infrastructure will be needed. This report contains a lot of detailed information about OA publishing pain points and supply chains, and also contains data such as librarian survey results about OA support, and case studies of publishers impacted.

See: <https://zenodo.org/records/14679068>

Springer OA Author Testimonials

This resource is a collection of author testimonials on the experience of publishing OA books. While such author experiences are valuable, and something we would like to collate in the InfoHub, we still need to determine, in collaboration with the working group, where our limits are in terms of what resources we are happy to platform. Is Springer on the other side of that line?

See: <https://www.springernature.com/gp/open-research/journals-books/books/testimonials>

Bloomsbury author case studies

This blog post is an interview with four authors who participated on the Bloomsbury Open Collections scheme for their African Studies and International Development list. In the interviews they cover good reasons regarding equity for diamond publishing, although since the questions were leading and focussed, it does not provide much information about the process widely. However, it would still be worth linking to this as an example of the author experience of diamond OA book publishing.

See: <https://www.bloomsbury.com/uk/discover/bloomsbury-academic/blog/featured/open-access-and-the-global-south-the-barriers-the-benefits-and-the-future/>

University of Oxford Open book case studies

Provides case studies from different career stages, outlines some common author concerns, showcases how OA can bypass some problems (e.g. it widens access to research, and it favours a primarily digital format which is better suited to some work). It is not told in the authors' own words which makes it less impactful but it would still be worth linking to, especially as this is with an HEI rather than a publisher (so a slightly different perspective).

See: <https://openaccess.ox.ac.uk/open-monographs#widget-id-4552841>

Lancaster University: Author Testimonies and Case Studies

This provides case studies from Lancaster University's researchers on publishing open access books. These are recorded via video interviews with the researchers. At the bottom of the page is a list of other author testimonials with links to those resources.

See: https://www.lancaster.ac.uk/articulate/OA_Books/#!/lessons/rEa3DYjldI7d1iJ_Uac4DR49DOqUMia4

Classifying Open Access business models

This resource is an article offering a comprehensive classification system for OA models, categorising them into five core types (transactional, bundled, cooperative, sponsored, and alternative), each with distinct characteristics and implications for funding, equity, and implementation. It is extremely new, and the author is refining it on the basis of feedback (including from Copim members), and is very comprehensive and clear, and also does not use the colour coding system. Definitely a good resource to link to.

See: <https://zenodo.org/records/11242106>

SCURL EDI Network: EDI toolkit

This toolkit from SCURL EDI Network aims to support member libraries in embedding good practice consistently across services. It is comprehensive and useful and comes at the topic from several angles - that of evaluating EDI in the workplace and recruitment, but also from policy and how to support students in the library. The plan is to annually evaluate and update it, and the resource is very recent (from 2023). It covers the topic from a library POV but has more widely applicable sections (e.g. on hiring policies). Good toolkit - but specifically library (and UK)-focussed so does not fulfill the publisher's perspective need - overall a very good resource for EDI in libraries.

See: <https://www.scurl.ac.uk/edi-toolkit-home>

Business Models for Open Access Books

This is a collection of case studies detailing the business models of a range of open access (OA) academic book presses. While they are extremely detailed, they have not been updated since 2022 and are therefore a little out of date. However, this is definitely still a resource to signpost to.

See: <https://oabooksbusinessmodels.pubpub.org/>

Open Access Network: Open Access Books summary Infohub

A German language (English option available) online summary info hub on OA books. Comprehensive coverage of all things OA but content probably covered in other resources.

See: <https://open-access.network/en/information/publishing/open-access-books>

Sherpa Open Access for Books (Jisc)

Long awaited addition to Jisc's well established Sherpa toolsuite of resources (journals) - developed to support the UKRI OA policy for longform, it is still relatively new (released early 2024) and a limited number of publisher data sets included. This is increasing and it will move to live release in autumn 2024. Strong sector and funder support.

See: <https://beta.sherpa.ac.uk/oa-books>

OPERAS Pathfinder

A publication service finder for editorial managers, editors and authors at any stage of a publication project. Useful resource as caters for different stakeholder groups; currently in beta so not fully developed but hosted by Operas so watch this space...

See: <https://pathfinder.operas-eu.org/>

University of Sheffield OA author case studies

Good to see HEIs showcasing good practice at their institutions, author advocacy is likely to be far more useful in winning hearts and minds of academics than policies/mandates.

See: <https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/library/open-access/books/open-access-monographs-case-studies>

Open access book publishing: a series editor writes

OBP blog doesn't have a huge audience, it would need resource to push out more widely. Are the views of an established Cam academic widely representative of academics, will they have much effect?

See: <https://blogs.openbookpublishers.com/open-access-book-publishing-a-series-editor-writes/>

Scottish Universities Press: Breaking down borders between academia and the rest of the world: A conversation with Tim Ingold and his co-authors

In this blog post, SUP interviews the authors of their first OA books on why they decided to publish open access, and about the research and writing process of the book. They also discuss the aims and effects of making academic research available to a wider audience.

See: <https://www.sup.ac.uk/news/tim-ingold-blog-post>

UKRI: Researchers' experiences of publishing academic books open access. Case studies on open access publishing

This collection of 16 case studies, published by UKRI in 2025, showcases the authors' perspectives on publishing open access. The case studies, the result of interviews with the authors, all have slightly different focuses, guided by the authors' perspectives, experiences and histories, but all cover the perceived benefits of publishing work openly - not just to the authors but everyone.

See: <https://zenodo.org/records/13944972>

ASK UP

Rotating presses give first hand experience answers. Also an FAQ section and list of previously curated answers. We like the idea, unsure how widely used it is.

See: <https://ask.up.hcommons.org/submit-a-question/>

Experimental Publishing Compendium

A comprehensive online resource created by Copim's Experimental Publishing Group bringing together tools, practices, and books to promote and support the publication of experimental book publications. Shows the advantages and opportunities that online publishing can offer for innovative collaboration, interactions and experimentations.

See: <https://compendium.copim.ac.uk/>

Contracts in Publishing: A toolkit for authors and publishers

Is it focused on journals or books? Does it matter? Comprehensive resource and not like anything else on the market (that we've been able to find).

See: <https://www.wipo.int/publications/en/details.jsp?id=4742&plang=EN>

How to Start an Open Access Journal: 2024 Small Publisher Primer

The Primer is a guide for those working with a scholarly society or institution to launch an OA journal in-house. Comprehensive resource for journals to flip to OA but do we need to include as no mention of OA books.

See: <https://blog.scholasticahq.com/post/how-to-start-flip-open-access-academic-journal/>

TOME Author Testimonials

An unusual author experience resource that consists of a series of video interviews rather than written accounts, that detail author experiences with TOME.

See: <https://www.openmonographs.org/tome-author-testimonials/>

TOME Report: The Cost to Publish TOME Monographs

A study of the costs incurred by US university presses in publishing scholarly monographs as part of the TOME pilot project. While it is very focussed on US institutional publishing, with extremely high costs that do not necessarily map onto those in the UK and elsewhere, we aim to include it in the proposed section of the InfoHub on flipping to OA as it is highly relevant.

See: <https://hcommons.org/deposits/item/hc:47235/>

TOME Stakeholder Value Assessment: Final Report

A concluding report about the author experiences with the TOME project, and more general conclusions about how the groundwork with authors and universities would need to be built on by any subsequent projects, and relevant to the proposed section of the InfoHub on flipping to OA.

See: <https://www.arl.org/resources/tome-stakeholder-value-assessment-final-report/>

University of Essex OA fund author testimonials

A series of interviews with OA authors at Essex who have used their Open Access Fund. It is very new, but likely to remain hosted on the Essex blog as Essex are extremely proactive and positive when it comes to supporting more equitable, alternative publishing models. Definitely worth including in our author experiences although it is not diamond OA.

See: <https://www.essex.ac.uk/blog/authors/sean-andersson>

EIFL Report 'Landscape of no-fee open access publishing in Africa'

A landscape study on Diamond OA journals in Africa which provides detailed reports for several countries and thorough general conclusions about the state of Diamond OA journals in the region, their current challenges, and suggestions for the future. It also provides the survey data which provides a large amount of granular data.

Cookbook for Open Access books

Language Science Press is a born-digital scholar-led open access publisher in linguistics so a good example of what can be achieved. The book is available for collaborative reading at <https://paperhive.org/documents/remote?type=langsci&id=cookbook> Readers can directly annotate the text there, raise questions, make comments or share personal experiences. Source code is also freely available. It doesn't claim to be written by experts but is complemented by the business model (<https://zenodo.org/record/1286972>), open business data, and a spreadsheet for drafting and calculating own business models.

See: <https://zenodo.org/records/1286925>

Open Science resources | Latin America

Visual / interactive dashboard which should be included in the scoping report as an example of a multilingual, regional / RoW resource.

See: <https://lookerstudio.google.com/u/0/reporting/c1c867bd-1b60-4241-8584-9423c10c081b/page/jyqmD>

OA Book Stakeholders (African Context)

This relational diagram is an unparalleled resource in a very under-described region for OA books. While the [EIFL report on OA in Africa](#) is very detailed and informative it only deals with journals, while this focuses on books. The relationships are not always clear, and since this is a relational diagram it is not very descriptive, but it is a very useful starting point.

The PDF of the relational diagram and the mission statement accompanying it are available on the Copim Compass (directly hosted on that resource).

Canadian Library Journal Publishing: A Primer

This is a primer, produced by the Canadian Association of Research Libraries in 2024, on library publishing in Canada. It has a focus on journal publishing. As well as providing a brief summary of the support available to journals at CARL libraries, it also summarises some of the core principles of library journal publishing more widely to do with commerciality and fees, diversity, and discovery/preservation. CARL have also produced further reports, some of which are region-specific, such as [copyright for Crown-published works](#), and on [OER policy and infrastructure](#). A full list of their outputs is here: <https://www.carl-abrc.ca/publications-and-documents/>

See: <https://www.carl-abrc.ca/publications-and-documents/>

Open Access Australasia

This association, Open Access Australasia, advocates for and supports practical initiatives on open access in Australia and Aotearoa New Zealand. It is a large community, with several written resources, groups, directories, and others.

See: <https://oaaustralasia.org/>

How to flip your journal: A guide to more equitable publishing with Diamond Open Access

This guide, an output of the *Strengthening Diamond OA in the Netherlands* [project](#), is a comprehensive guide to the rationale and logistics of flipping a journal to Diamond OA; what routes are available, how they work, the financial aspect, and case studies for implementation. While it is speaking primarily to the Dutch context, the suggestions are more widely applicable.

See: <https://zenodo.org/records/14652446>

Guidance on managing copyright under UKRI open access policy

This report by UKRI from 2023 provides guidance and explanations on third party copyright in the UK context when dealing with open access. It is aimed at researchers (and research organisations), who are seeking clarity on copyright for their open access publications.

See: <https://www.ukri.org/publications/guidance-on-managing-copyright-under-ukri-open-access-policy/>

Publishing under the UKRI open access policy: copyright and Creative Commons licences

This guide, written by Jisc, provides guidance on the UKRI open access policy as it pertains to copyright; both third party permissions for open access work, but also on authors' copyright and moral rights when they publish OA, the different licences available to them, and copyright exceptions. It covers both books and journals.

See: <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/guides/copyright-and-creative-commons-licences-for-publishing-under-the-ukri-open-access-policy>

An introduction to UKRI's fund for longform outputs

This is a guide for UKRI-funded authors on how to use the UKRI research fund to make their longform works immediately available open access (mandatory since early 2024). It sets out the available funding limits for BPCs, CPCs and for OA subscription funds. It also sets out the application process.

See: <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/guides/an-introduction-to-ukris-fund-for-longform-outputs>

Plan S: New tool to assess equity in scholarly communication models

This online assessment tool, launched in 2024, enables self-assessment of financial models by funders, publishers and others about access to read, access to publish (with or without fee), reuse rights, fee transparency, and promoting open data and code, and preprints and open peer review. While this is, at least currently, explicitly for journals, and implicitly more relevant to STEM subjects (e.g. open code) much of it is applicable to books and to AHSS subjects.

See: <https://www.coalition-s.org/new-tool-to-assess-equity-in-scholarly-communication-models/>

Manchester University Press Alt Text Guidelines

This resource provides clear guidelines for creating alt text for images in books in order to make them more accessible. It also links to other guidance, such as from United Nations Publications.

See: <https://manchesteruniversitypress.co.uk/alt-text-guidelines/>

DIAMAS Best Practices checklist for Diamond OA publishers

This self-assessment checklist is for publishers of Diamond OA books and journals. It provides guidelines for best practice in several areas (e.g. governance, funding, editorial integrity) and provides suggestions for improvement. It also provides external links for more information to support these guidelines.

See: <https://diamasproject.eu/best-practices-checklist-for-diamond-oa-publishers/>

DIAMAS Resources & Guidelines

This page hosts links to a number of DIAMAS resources on Diamond OA publishing. While many are journal-specific, some are more generic and/or aimed at Diamond OA publishers more generally. Included are a series of high-level and in-depth articles about Diamond OA publishing, DOAS (the Diamond Open Access Standard), and its components. It also contains self-assessment tools, a glossary, and a number of resources on sustainability for publishers, service providers and funders.

See: <https://toolsuite.diamas.org/tools-and-resources>

European University Association: The new university Open Access checklist

This checklist, produced in 2021, made recommendations for advocacy and actions to support open access implementation within universities. These are categorised into: empowering the university, building capacity, and reinforcing this capacity. It also provides clear parameters, rationales, suggestions for action, and expected outcome of these actions. While this report was aimed at universities as research centres and funders, it is extremely useful for publishers regarding the possible perspectives and strategic goals of universities.

See: <https://www.eua.eu/publications/reports/the-new-university-open-access-checklist.html>

Library Partnership Rating

This project, developed by US librarians, seeks to quantify the alignment between publisher's practices and library values. To achieve this they have created a rubric of measurable practices.

It has been referenced and adopted by other librarians in developing comparable rubrics. Currently, this focuses on journals although as of early 2025, they are working to develop a version for books.

See: <https://library-partnership-rating.pubpub.org/>

Open Access Books Network: 'Mythbusters' video series

A video series by OABN to dispel key myths around OA books that may put prospective authors off. These address often-asked questions in an approachable and helpful way, and the answers are provided by relevant external partners including OA authors.

See: <https://openaccessbooksnetwork.hcommons.org/oa-mythbusters/>

Open Access Books Network: Around the World with the OABN

A series of blog posts which focus on OA books in a different country around the world, highlighting their regional experiences, problems and successes. This is an ongoing series that is still being updated, and unlike many OA resources provides (emic) perspectives from beyond the ERA.

See: <https://openaccessbooksnetwork.hcommons.org/category/around-the-world-with-the-oabn/>

OAPEN Author Success Stories

A collection of case study interviews with authors who explain in their own words how OA has benefited their work. They come from a range of disciplines, geographical areas, and publishers, and all explore different, but related, reasons for why OA was a successful choice for them.

See: <https://www.oabooks-toolkit.org/the-oabooks-landscape/7555171-author-success-stories>

Copim WP7 Report on Archiving and Preserving Open Access Monographs

A report on the Copim Project's knowledge and recommendation on archiving and preservation. It provides guidance for smaller, scholar-led presses on metadata, archiving and preservation, on repositories, and on the Thoth Archiving Network.

See: <https://zenodo.org/records/7876048>

Appendix 3. Useful organisations, projects and platforms

Thoth

Thoth is a non-profit, open metadata management and dissemination platform. An active and successful outreach campaign has enabled revenue targets to be met. Thoth integrates into third party platforms, these collaborations enable seamless access to Thoth's metadata management and distribution capabilities across diverse scholarly platforms.

See: <https://thoth.pub/> and <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki>

OPERAS Metrics

OPERAS, referenced elsewhere in this report in different capacities, offers metrics about the usage and impact of OA books, providing consolidated usage data for the publisher's website but also other sites where the book is available.

See: <https://operas-eu.org/services/metrics-service/>

OIPA (including useful resources)

The Open Institutional Publishing Association (OIPA) was founded to connect and encourage open access publishing within the UK. Our mission is to create a new source of support and advocacy for established and emerging university presses and institutionally-affiliated publishing operations striving for open access. A fairly new organisation open to UK-based institutional OA publishers. Their website contains a list of useful resources which they have plans to expand as per member needs. Relatively limited but a reliable resource and probably the go to for UK-based IPs.

See: <https://oipauk.org/useful-resources/>

OASPA

OASPA is a diverse community of organisations engaged in open scholarship with a mission to encourage and enable open access as the predominant model of communication for scholarly outputs. OASPA encourage and enable open access as the predominant model of communication for scholarly outputs - good to signpost to them in our resource.

See: <https://www.oaspa.org/>

AUP

AUP is a membership organisation of nonprofit scholarly publishers, publishing to high editorial and professional standards. It is a strong collective group, and would be useful to include / sign post to in the OBF toolkit.

See: <https://aupresses.org/>

Library Publishing Coalition (LPC)

The LPC is an independent, community-led membership association of academic and research libraries and library consortia engaged in scholarly publishing. Their website features a range of useful materials. It is a strong collective group, and would be useful to include / sign post to in the OBF toolkit.

See: <https://librarypublishing.org/>

Association of European University Presses (AEUP)

The AEUP is an organisation of and for university presses across Europe to help them build stronger relationships between them, to co-operate and share knowledge in order to reach common goals and to jointly address important issues in publishing. It is a strong collective group, and would be useful to include / sign post to in the OBF toolkit.

See: <https://www.aeup.eu/>

Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB)

DOAB is a discovery service indexing and providing access to peer reviewed, scholarly open access books. It also serves as a marker of trust for users. It is a crucial platform that needs to be supported and used.

See: <https://www.doabooks.org/>

One of its services is PRISM: Peer Review Information Service for Monographs. It is a standardised way for publishers to display information about their peer review processes, aiming to provide transparency about publishing and thus build trust in the quality of OA books. Excellent resource for multiple audiences, should be included.

See: <https://www.doabooks.org/en/article/prism>

Publishers must be accepted both into DOAB generally and into PRISM, so the service as a whole works to improve the reputation of OA.

Open access tracking project

Interesting community project and good source of information eg. tracking, collating and sharing on social media.

See: https://cyber.harvard.edu/hoap/Open_Access_Tracking_Project

Open Access Books Network (OABN)

A shared community space / network for those interested in all things OA books, non judgemental, informal and open to all stakeholder groups. It also has its own FAQs, blog posts and other information. A great space for passionate conversations around OA books, it should be supported!

See: <https://openaccessbooksnetwork.hcommons.org/>

Project Muse

Large scale platform (and aggregator) focusing on humanities output, not uniquely OA content, could be used as an e.g. of where the reader could look for content.

See: <https://muse.jhu.edu/>

Open Research Library

The Open Research Library (ORL) is planned to include all Open Access book content worldwide on one platform for user-friendly discovery, offering a seamless experience navigating more than 14,000 Open Access books. HOWEVER - tied to Knowledge Unlatched (KU) and has limited coverage.

See: <https://openresearchlibrary.org/home>

Open Research Community

The Open Research Community (ORC) is an online space owned by KU and while it offers a variety of resources and space for discussion and collaboration, as above, the connection with KU makes it an unsuitable resource to sign post to.

See: <https://openresearch.community/>

JSTOR Open Access

The open access portal for JSTOR, a large scale platform and aggregator for (largely HSS) books, journals, images and primary sources; could be used as an e.g. of where the reader could look for content.

See: <https://about.jstor.org/oa-and-free/>

The Publishers Learning and Community Exchange (PLACE)

A helpful forum offering information on publishing processes and standards, developed by a coalition of Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE), Crossref, the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) and the Open Access Scholarly Publishers Association (OASPA). Currently journals - focused, do we want to include when the monographs space has OABN etc.

See: <https://theplace.discourse.group/>

Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO)

SciELO is an index and database of books and journals, which hosts several OA titles. It focuses on articles from Latin America and South Africa, in Spanish, Portuguese, and English. These are largely scientific titles.

See: <https://books.scielo.org/en/introducion/>

Ulibros

Ulibros is the platform of EU_LAC. It helps publishers to facilitate and streamline metadata management, and also hosts a repository of OA book titles from across the region.

See: <https://ulibros.com/>

SPARC Europe

SPARC Europe are a Dutch foundation advocating for open access, open science, open scholarship and open education within Europe. They collaborate with numerous European stakeholders to attempt to shape policy maximising the access and reuse of research and educational resources.

See: <https://sparceurope.org/>

OAPEN

The OAPEN Foundation is a non-profit dedicated to open access, peer reviewed books, hosting their central repository, the OAPEN Toolkit detailed above, and also DOAB. It aims to increase visibility and retrievability of high-quality OA publications and promote OA book publishing. It provides crucial services for a number of stakeholder groups.

See: <https://www.oapen.org/>

It also hosts the OAPEN repository for hosting and disseminating OA books. We should link directly to it for readers/researchers.

See: <https://library.oapen.org/>

TOME

Towards an Open Monograph Ecosystem is a US-based project aimed at changing the way monograph publishing in the humanities and social sciences is funded. It seems like a good initiative with buy in from IPs but as the outcome is unknown, unlikely to include (unless as an eg. of OA initiatives)

See: <https://www.openmonographs.org/>

Appendix 4. In development

Information Power

Information Power has been commissioned by UKRI, in partnership with the Association of Learned Society Publishers (ALPSP), the British Academy, and the Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association (OASPA), to support book publishers in their transition to sustainable open access models, with a particular focus on learned society, subject association, and smaller specialist publishers.¹⁸

The overall objective of this project is to develop advice, options, and a toolkit for learned society, subject associations, and smaller specialist publishers to help them explore and embrace open access for academic book publishing. The project deliverables will include a report and a practical toolkit.

¹⁸ <https://www.informationpower.co.uk/open-access-transitions-for-book-publishers-spa-ops-4-0/>

The project deliverables (a report and a practical toolkit) sound promising but will need to see the published version before making a decision on inclusion.

See: <https://www.informationpower.co.uk/open-access-transitions-for-book-publishers-spa-ops-4-0/>

DIAMAS project

The project has provided an excellent temperature check of the current IPSP landscape across Europe so far, and has delivered resources such as Diamond Open Access Quality (DOAS). A technical guide and a practical benchmarking resource, DOAS combines comprehensive guidelines with a self-assessment tool to elevate standards in scholarly publishing. When the project is complete, the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) will serve as a hub and a web portal for scholarly publishing service providers in Europe and will lay the foundation of a future Diamond Capacity Center (DCC): a virtual network of resources and platforms enabling capacity building, networking and knowledge exchange.

See: <https://diamasproject.eu/>

PALOMERA project

The PALOMERA project is funded by the European Union for two years under the Horizon Europe program. In a nutshell, it seeks to understand why so few OA funder policies include books, and to provide actionable recommendations to change this.

As part of phase 1 of the project, the Knowledge Base was created. A collection of documents such as reports, policies, statistics, survey results and interview transcripts relevant to OA policies regarding OA books in the ERA, it is hosted on OAPEN's website, and includes over 600 documents in various languages, open to anyone to browse and read. The Knowledge Base aims to help the community as a first step towards a better overview of what documents exist or are available.

See: <https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/>

Invest in Open Infrastructure (IOI)

IOI is an organisation that aims to increase investment in and use of open infrastructure by releasing guidelines and a tool (Infra Finder) to search and compare open infrastructure. Infra Finder serves as a free, one-stop discovery and evaluation tool for users to find open infrastructure services that may suit their needs. It is still early days but but community driven tool, supporting open research infrastructure is vital for LT sustainability of OA books.

See: <https://investinopen.org/> and

<https://investinopen.org/blog/blog-introducing-infra-finder/> n.b. OA toolkit maybe we will need to break this down into sections (same goes for some other larger, comprehensive resources I think).

OASPA (recommendations to increase equity in open access)

OASPA have recently invited feedback on their draft recommended practices to increase equity in open access (OA). The intention is that the finalised version of these recommended practices will be a helpful and supportive framework for all publishing organisations seeking to build more equity and facilitate broader participation in OA. After revisions, the finalised version will be released in a more engaging format, with a DOI, under a CC BY license. OASPA also expect to generate a checklist for the more objective aspects of these recommendations.

See: <https://www.oaspa.org/news/oaspa-calls-for-community-feedback-on-draft-recommendations-to-increase-equity-in-open-access/>

OIPA resources hub

Although OIPA has already gathered together a list of resources (including documents, toolkits and platforms) and organisations providing support for open access publishing in different ways for their member organisations (and anyone interested in finding out more about open access publishing more generally) on their website, they are planning on creating a more comprehensive InfoHub. OIPA are close allies of the OBF and we need to work closely together to align ideas and objectives.

Copim OBF project: WP5

One of the deliverables for the accessibility work package is to publish "Guidance on accessibility standards implementation (online toolkit). You can keep up with the group's work at: <https://copim.pubpub.org/accessibility>